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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO KNOW ABOUT THE OCULAR
TRAUMA PATTERN IN A SECONDARY CARE HOSPITAL**¹Dr Seemab Fatima, ²Dr Sameen Aslam, ³Dr. Wajiha Irfan¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore, ²Fauji Foundation Hospital, Rawalpindi, ³House Officer, Ibn-E-Siena Hospital & Research Institute Multan.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:****Background:** Ocular trauma is prominent emergency situation.**Objectives:** This study was done to know about the ocular trauma pattern in a secondary care hospital of Lahore.**Subjects and Methods:** This study was done in eye department of Mayo Hospital Lahore. The time period of this study was two years. Five and six patients showing ocular trauma were selected. Detailed medical history including complete examination was written in a questionnaire. Statistical analysis was also done.**Result:** Among 506 selected patients, 77.7% 22.3% were male and female respectively. 145 patients were worker 90 patients were house wife. Mostly trauma cases were reported within few hours. Injury commonly occurs at workplace and at home. 80% patients were found with mechanical trauma. Mostly eyelid was injured in the trauma cases. Deep cut involving full thickness was seen in 38.9 patients.**Conclusion:** Conjoined open globe traumatic globe injuries were most commonly observed. Their chances observed. Their chances can be reduced with preventive measures.**Keywords:** Ocular emergency, trauma, globe injuries.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Seemab Fatima,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Eyes although occupies less space i.e. 0.27% on anterior body and 0.1% on overall body but their function is of great importance [1]. Due to injuries, eyes is mostly after feet and hands. Ocular trauma changes the life of its affects in decreasing job opportunities, physical disbalance and changing in life patterns [2]. Directly or indirectly, these eye related injuries can create work loss as well as disease [3]. It also creates permanent blindness. Almost half of patients admitted in eye department belong to eye injures [4]. It is worldwide estimation that 2.3 million cases of inspired vision, 1.6 million cases of impaired vision, 19 million cases of one eye blindness and impaired vision are because of injuries [5]. Yearly estimation of eye injuries in United State is over 2.4 million and this is main reason for being hospitalized [6].

Hospital data has shown 9.54% admission in eye department in developing countries are because of eye injuries [7]. Various kind of activities pose different risks for eye injuries. In one study, it was shown that mostly patients with eye injuries are less than 30 years old [8]. Severe eyes injuries occur in developing counties. Timely diagnosis and preventive measures can help stay safe from eyes injuries and their complication [9,10,11]. Protective wear can reduce eye injuries are common in our society but still it is not recognized considerably. There is no registration system system for such injuries. This study was done to know about eye injuries pattern in secondary care hospital in District Lahore.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

This study took 2 years to be completed.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients of both genders above one-year age with severe eye injuries were selected.

Exclusion Criteria:

- New born children and infants:
- Patients showing eye swelling, post injury and post-surgery infections.
- Patients not requiring immediate attention. Severely multiple organ injured.

- All patients were selected on basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Comprehensive medical history and demographic information was collected from patients or their parents. Patients examination was done according to standard methods.
- Injuries of children were evaluated under anesthesia. In case of base or acid burns, assessment was done after washing the eye properly. Physical injuries were checked after providing stable emergency treatment. The digital X-rays examination was done in case of orbital fractures. The information was analyzed by SPSS version 22.

RESULTS:

This study was done at eye department of Mayo Hospital Lahore. There were two groups of patients. 506 patients were included in non-infectious injury sub groups. Thirty patients were placed in infectious sub groups and this was excluded from the study. There were 393 males and 113 females. Out of total patients, 145 were workers, 90 were house wives and 72 were farmers.

In 251 patients, right eye injury was involved, left eye was affected in 204 patients and both eye in 51 patients. Most common injury place was found to be home. In 288 patients, physical blunt injury was found. In 117 patients, physical sharp injury was reported. Accident was the major cause of injuries and violence being the second one. In spots, ball caused most of the injuries. 225 patients were having their outer membrane of eye disrupted and full thickness injuries to cornea or sclera or both. Fifty patients showed physical open globe injury. Corneal perforation was observed in 18 patients, limbal in 10 and perforation of sclera in a patient. Close globe injury was due to the death of cell groups on corneal groups surface and it was present in 20 patients. In most trauma cases, eyelid was injured. Deep cut involving full thickness was seen in 151 patients.

Table I: Occupation and sex distribution

Occupation	Sex of patient		Total (%)
	Male	Female	
Pre school	5	1	6 (1.2%)
Student	51	12	63 (12.5%)
Housewife	0	90	90 (17.8 %)
Worker	135	10	145 (28.7%)
Farmer	72	0	72 (14.2%)
Welder	42	0	42 (8.3%)
Driver	22	0	22 (4.3 %)
Businessman	20	0	20 (4.0%)
Jobless	46	0	46 (9.1%)
Total	393	113	506 (100.0%)

Table II: Place and nature of injury and sex distribution

Place of injury	Sex of patient		Total (%)
	Male	Female	
Home	45	102	147 (29.1%)
Industry/ Work place	129	4	133 (26.3%)
Farm	48	0	48 (9.5%)
School	21	3	24 (4.7%)
Play ground	20	2	22 (4.3%)
Underconstruction building	29	0	29 (5.7%)
Street/ Highway	101	2	103 (20.4%)
Total	393	113	506 (100%)

Nature of injury	Sex of patient		Total (%)
	Male	Female	
Mechanical blunt	234	54	288 (56.9%)
Mechanical Sharp	100	17	117 (23.1%)
Thermal	15	11	26 (5.1%)
Acid	24	7	31 (6.1%)
Base	9	15	24 (4.7%)
Superglue	11	9	20 (4.0%)
Total	393	113	506 (100%)

Table III: Physical Objects causing injury and sex distribution

Cause	Objects	Sex of patient		Total
		Male	Female	
Accidental (322, 63.6%)	Wood	24	14	38
	Stick	37	14	51
	Knife	17	2	19
	Scissors	6	3	9
	Thorn	6	3	9
	Syringe needle	0	1	1
	Glass	12	2	14
	Animal bite	6	2	8
	Hammering on metal	14	0	14
	Welding	6	0	6

	Pressure Cooker blast	05	5	10
	Battery explosion	17	0	17
	Superglue	7	0	7
	Machine injury	30	2	32
	Iron rod	31	6	37
	Chemical splash	13	1	14
	Domestic activity	0	36	36
Assault (n= 169, 33.4%)	Stone throwing	17	4	21
	Finger/Fist	41	3	44
	Road traffic accident	39	3	42
	Bomb blast	4	0	4
	Firearm	14	2	16
Sports (n= 15, 3%)	Stick	32	9	41
	Catapult	2	0	2
	Gullidanda	2	1	3
	Firecracker	2	0	2
	Ball	6	0	6
	Toy pistol pallet	2	0	2

Table IV: Presenting visual acuity of traumatized eye and sex distribution.

Presenting visual acuity	Sex of patient		Total
	Male	Female	
No perception of light	8	2	10 (2.0%)
Perception of light	101	34	135 (26.7%)
Hand movement	132	30	162 (32.0 %)
Counting finger	79	30	109 (21.5 %)
1/60-6/60	29	15	44 (8.7%)
> 6/60	20	1	21 (4.2 %)
Un co-operative	24	1	25 (4.9 %)
Total	393	113	506 (100%)

Table V: Cause of Globe injury and sex distribution

Cause	Sex of patient		Total
	Male	Female	
Mechanical open globe	46	4	50
Corneal perforation	16	2	18
Scleral perforation	9	0	9
Corneoscleral perforation	12	1	13
Limbal perforation	9	1	10
Mechanical close globe	41	27	68
Hyphema	15	3	18
Iridodialysis	5	1	6
Traumatic cataract	4	1	5
Subluxated /dislocated lens	2	0	2
Vitreous haemorrhage	1	1	2
Corneal foreign body	9	6	15
Punctate keratitis	5	15	20
Total	87	31	118 (100%)

DISCUSSION:

In this study, 397 patients were male and 267 were between 11-40 years. This shows similarity of percentage with Jahangir T et al who reported 30% patients less than 45 years, Iqbal A et al reported 61.4% men less than 10 years and Jan S et al reported 35% men less than 40 years [13,14,15]. Lack of preventive measures, illiteracy and poverty may contribute to high ratio of injuries in men.

This study concluded that most of injuries occur in workers. In homes, most of injuries occurred followed by work place. These results are similar to that of Jahangir T et al, Desai et al [14,16]. In current study, mechanical trauma was most common due to blunt and sharp objects. These finding were opposite to that of Jahangir T et al, but in agreement with Malik RA et al and Jafri AK et al [14,17,25]. Accident trauma and the stick related injuries were most common and this was according to that of Baber TF et al [18].

Exam A et al reported violence in 62.2%, RTA in 20.5% and Baber TF et al reported violence injuries in 31.2% cases [2,18]. 17% eye injuries were because of stone throwing in our study and Soylu at al showed same results [19,20]. Baber TF et al reported sports related injuries in 13.5%, catapult in 36.9%, quildanda in 15.3% and ball in 3.07% patients. Jahangir T et al showed VA less than 6/60 in 79% cases and Malik RA et al reported 33.5% having VA as light perception. [14,17] Iqbal A et al and Baber TF et al reported DGI in 76.1% and 50.9% patients respectively [13,18]. Ibadan study and Hatton MP et al reported corneal perforation in 65% and 58% patients [21,22]. Malik RA et al showed 42% open globe injuries [17].

Mechanical close globe injury was presented in 58%, 37.3% and 16.3% according to , Malik RA et al, Baber TF et al and EL-Mekawey et al respectively [17,18,23]. Deep cut involving full thickness was demonstrated in 38.9% patients.

CONCLUSION:

Men, youth and unprotected eyes during high risk activities are more prone to ocular injuries. Awareness and preventive measures can reduce the higher risk rates for these injuries.

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